

Representation Through Lawyers In British India: Legal Analysis During The Reign Of Mughal Emperors And Classical Hindu Law

Rashida Zahoor, Muhammad Asif Safdar, Khurram Baig, Waqas Ahamad

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 11, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 13, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : British India, Lawyers, Mughal Emperor, Classical Hindu Law.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7316865</p>	<p><i>Lawyers do have many skills and these skills along with their other professional traits are usually culminated for the benefits of their clients. For Lawyer, the goals of their client are supreme. Though in order to keep their clients goals paramount; the Lawyers have to face some restrictions imposed by the conflicting interests of other persons or the general public as the case may be. There is very important role of Lawyers in the society for the administration of justice. The past of the legal profession and role of Lawyers has been expounded by many scholars in their writings. However, this article focuses on representation through Lawyers in British India and analyzing textual data of classical Hindu law. In the reign of Mughal emperors, particularly Muhiyuddin Muhammad Awrangzeb (1658-1707) representation through Lawyers was recognized and even till date the role of Lawyers plays a significant part in order to secure ends of justice and prevention of abuses. The paper critically discusses representation of lawyers, their role and duties in British India. In particular, it analyses the text of classical Hindu law by contextualizing text of Classical Hindu Books. Finally, it establishes that during the sovereignty of Aurangzeb, "Vakils" (lawyers) were designated in each district; for the first time in history; to defend the trials against the State. These Lawyers were called "Vakil-e-Sarkar" or "Vakil-e Shara". The classical Hindu law did recognize the representation through Lawyers.</i></p>

Introduction

Lawyers advocate for their clients' Interests. For such purpose, Lawyers do represent the interests of their clients in a wide range of areas. While doing these tasks Lawyers usually ignore the legitimate and vested interests of other people and sometimes the general public so that they may secure the interests of their clients which are definitely paramount to them and their professionalism. For a Lawyer, it is not shameful to efficiently represent the interests of his client and to decline the other people from gaining interests. The Lawyer definitely do this for the advantage of his client. This is absolutely a legitimate role of the lawyer in representation. The role of a Lawyer in society is very important.

A Lawyer knows only one person in the world in the performance of his duties, and that person is his client. The basic and primary duty of a Lawyer is to save the interests of his client as well as to represent the rights of him. While defending and representing his client in a secure way the Lawyer is also vigilant at the same time to not lose his case for himself. During this representation, a Lawyer must disregard the apprehension, the annoyance, the injury which he might bring to others. If he separates himself from the duty of a patriot that of a Lawyer, he should continue whatever the consequences, even if it may be his unfortunate destiny to confuse his country.

The role of a Lawyer does not bind him to represent a such client whose objectives and goals are repulsive and against his political, social, professional, moral or religious beliefs. Generally, Lawyers do not take this position lightly and usually not allow clients to detach them from their beliefs and opinions. In this context, it is argued for the support of this "limit" and to remove the fear that a client may not be adequately represented by a such repulsed Lawyer. Instead of this, good Lawyers are professionally proud of that Lawyer who is not hesitant even to represent the unknown client without giving any concern to others opinions. The Lawyers and their profession is proud of the ethics of separation from the moral position of the client. So, this "limit" is therefore hardly one at all. In British India the Lawyers play significant role in order to address the issues of the people. On the other hand, Classical Hindu Law also recognizes the legal profession and existence of this system.

With the above prelude, this work is divided into two parts. First part is related to the representation of Lawyers in British India in which specific attention is given to the era of Aurangzeb and Shahjahan. Further, the cases argued and pleaded by Lawyers are also listed. In this context, their remuneration, Elevation to bench and Lawyers in other departments of Shahjahan are also addressed. Second part focuses on the text of Classical

Hindu Law in which the slokas or stanzas have been taken from the relevant books and critically examined. Further, the opinion of highly qualified Scholars regarding the existence of Lawyers in classical Hindu law is also addressed. Finally, Conclusions will be drawn.

1. Analysis of Representation Through Lawyers in British India

Fiqh-e-Firoz Shahi and Fatawa-e-Alamgiria are the two Muslim Indian codes in which duties of Lawyers are mentioned. Another term applied to them was Vakils, even till date this term is used in Pakistan and India. There is specific chapter on the representation of Lawyer's i.e Kitabul-Vakalat in above mentioned books.

In the opinion of the Mawardi, if a person wants to become a practicing Lawyer or to be a Qazi then he must have sufficient knowledge of law. Without being expert in law and having adequate knowledge of law, a person cannot be a good Lawyer or a good Qazi. According to the Moreland, that the regular profession of Law did not exist there but contemporary authorities have referred to Vakils. (Hawala-e-vakil bayad kard een mard azan jamaat nest ki hamcshah ba yak taur saluk dashta bashand). Ibn Batuta who was a Judge in the reign of Muhammad Tughlaq (1315-1351) also speaks about Vakils. Badaoni refers to Rae Arzani, who was a Hindu Vakil of Khan Zaman. Sir Thomas Roe refers to his "Solicitor" who perused his plaint. The petition of the East India Company was presented by Lawyers on the original side of the Emperor's Court.

2.1. Leading Cases Argued by Lawyers:

According to Basheer Ahmed following cases were argued by Lawyers.

1. Amin Khan vs. Manucci. This case was theft Case.
2. East India Company vs. State. This case was Civil Case in which Ram Chander acted as Vakil.
3. State vs. Mir2a Beg Kotwal. This case was related to Murder in which Qawam Uddin argued the Case.
4. Haji Zahid and Pirji vs. State. It was Civil Suit in which Muhammad Mohsin acted as Vakil.
5. Mst. Feeta vs. Miran. This was Civil Suit.
6. Azmatullah vs. Ghulam Muhammad.
7. Khwajah Ahmad vs. Abi Muhammad.
8. Nusrat Ali vs. Qaim Ali.
9. Ata Husain vs. Ashiq Husan.

A high standard expected of Vakils is the "practice of law". Omar, the second caliph of Islam, said that he should be in good faith and sincerely plead the motive of his client. Vakils had a right to be heard before the courts and were attached to the personnel of each king and his sons. Lawyers were recognized and one Vakil was given the title of "Vakalat Khan" in the time of Bahadur Shah (1707- 1712) for his successful advocacy.

2.2. Vakil-e- Shara or Vakil-e-Sarkar:

A client could remove a Vakil and in this way withdraw the powers of his Vakil. During the rule of Shahjahan and Aurangzeb, Lawyers were hired to defend civil litigations against the state. They were also assigned with the task to assist poor litigants and to provide them free legal advice. The name given to them was Vakil-e-Shara. The Vakils had to file their "powers of attorney" (Vakalat Namah) in all cases. Today such practice is same in Pakistan and India. Lawyers are supposed to present their Vakalat-Nama in the Court before pleading case.

The East India Company authorised the Supreme Court of Calcutta to "approve, admit and enroll as many advocates and attorneys at law" as shall seem fit to the court" under the Regulation Act, 1773. However, these attorneys and solicitors were only English, Irish, and Scottish. Later on, the East India Company also permitted the Supreme Courts of Bombay and Madras to admit and enrol such attorneys. Yet the Indian Lawyer had no right to appear before the courts. However, in 1793 a regular profession authorizing the Sadar Diwani Adalat to enrol pleaders or vakeels, both Hindus and Muslims, for all Company's courts was created under the reform of Cornwallis.

2.3. Remuneration given to Vakil-e Shara:

Remuneration was given by the State to the Vakil-e-Sharai at the rate of Rupee. one a day. Therefore, these Vakils were also paid on the same rate and they used to take a fee of Rupee one per day for their services. The job of these Vakils was to provide the free legal assistance and advice to the poor. Chief Qazi of the Province was authorised to appoint these Vakils and in some cases the Chief Justice (Qazi-ul-Quzat) was also empowered to designate them. Today in Pakistan and India such Lawyers are State prosecutors and State gives them remuneration. It is not clear that what fees were charged by other Vakils from their clients. The order of Aurangzeb directing the State Vakils to offer free advice to paupers, recommends that the practice of accepting 'Mahentanah' was in trend. No receipts of payments have come to my notice, and the decrees in Baqiat do not mention the fees of the Vakils.

Whereas, Vakil-e-Sarkar or Vakil-e-Shara were appointed as full-time Lawyers in every district. These Vakils were attached to the Court of District Qadi. Their job was to plead the suits against the State. They were given remuneration at the rate of Rupee. one per day. Further, they were officially bound to provide free legal advice to the needy and poor people. State suits were also represented by these Vakils. Moreover, the execution of decrees on behalf of state were also ensured by these Vakils. In his correspondence, Sir Thomas, speaks about

“Solicitor” but this impression may be taken as parallel to a legal advisor and not in the sense of a Vakil-i-Sarkar.

2.4. Bar Associations:

There was no culture of Bar Associations as the Medieval Government was not based on modern democratic ideas. At that time there was no demand for such public organisations.

2.5. Elevation to Bench:

As recorded elsewhere, Vakils could be appointed Qazis in the districts where they were practising. A perusal of judgments in Baqiat shows that Qazi Qaim All was a local Lawyer and officiated as Qazi for some time. After he left the Bench he again appeared as a Lawyer in *Dunia Murai vs. Mir Shahamat* for the Defendant.

2.6. Vakil in other Departments:

The word 'Vakil' was also a general term applied in those days to Agents. Shahjahan's 'diplomatic' representative at the Court of Aurangzeb was referred to as “Vakil-e-An Hazrat”, "Waqea'at-e- Alamgir". At another place Sujana Rae in his *Khulasat ut Tawarikh* has used the word Vakil us Saltanat or Vakil-e-Mutalaq for the Prime Minister.

2.7. In case of Pauper Suits:

There is no record of any indulgence being granted to pauper litigants, before the time of Aurangzeb. In his reign the Vakils Shara were required to give advice free to the needy and the miserable and according to Sarkar the Court fees, if any, were paid by the State.

2. Classical Hindu Law:

Ancient Hindu law recognized that parties have a right to be represented through other persons. It is necessary to find out that are such persons “Lawyers”? In present time such person’s referred to as pleaders, advocates, Vakils, Lawyers. The question arises that did such persons correspond to the modern Lawyers who safeguard the interests of the people. Ancient Hindu law did recognize such persons as Lawyers. There was a class of experts who provided legal services to the parties in suit in order to secure and protect their rights. Even in other countries i.e Pakistan, United Kingdom, Canada and USA such persons provide their service by way of giving legal opinions on law questions and pleading cases. It is said that by looking at Hindu law this concept was also borrowed by the west in later half of 18th century. For this purpose, it is very much necessary to analysis the textual Hindu law in order to understand the above mentioned discussion.

3.1. Various Codes and opinion of Scholars:

In this section firstly, the opinions of scholars who accept the existence of Lawyers is discussed and then textual data will be analyzed.

The Halhed's Code of Gentoo Laws (1777) is considered one of the most important document in this regard. As it translates the *Vivadarnavasetu*. There is an explicit chapter titled “Of appointing Vakeel”. These are also translated as attorneys or Vakils. This chapter explicitly speaks about Lawyers. It states that: Because of any reason a person being plaintiff or defendant is unable to appear before the court then in such case he may appoint another person who may represent him before court on his behalf. Such representative shall be known as Vakeel and this Vakeel will represent his principal as plaintiff or defendant as the case may be. Further, in this situation if the case is won by the Vakeel his principal will also win the case.

In a case where the accusation of murder, robbery, adultery, consumption of prohibited foods, misuse, in chastity the modesty of an unmarried female, false testimony, destruction of anything or injuring the property of a judge, Vakeel should not be appointed to plead and respond in such cases; principles shall be asked and respond personally. But a woman, a lunatic, an idiot, a minor and anyone who is unable to make a difference between good and bad and cannot represent himself properly may be represented by a vakeel even in such heinous cases.

One eminent authority drew conclusion that each party has right to appear at the stage of trial and the representation was through persons. Today, such persons are known as Lawyers. The persons who gave their legal advices to clients are recognized in Indian law. They constitute numerous professions in India. They are also known as Advocate. Jolly in his book recognized the existence of legal profession in India by translating various classical Hindu law books. In this context, it seems that Jolly believed in the existence of Lawyers as well. He supported the representation through Lawyers under classical Hindu law.

3.2. Existence Recognised by other Scholars:

The existence of legal practitioners is also argued by other scholars. Few of them who support the existence are as follows:

1. The existence of legal practitioners such as, Lawyers in ancient India has been recognized and maintained, quite independently of Jolly, by Indian scholars. One of them was K. P. Jayaswal. He was ancient professional Lawyer. He was Lawyer from the time of Manusmrti and perhaps even earlier. He translated Manusmrti and wrote as follows:

The verse says that those who suffer for others are witnesses, guarantees and judges, but that those who benefit from the legislation are the king (“who obtains the costs of justice as court’s fee”), the creditor (“who

obtains his decree"), the merchant ("the speculator who provides the defendant with money for defense and in return acquires his property") and the Brahmin. This Brahmin is the Brahmin who counselled each party on the law. . . . The definition of Vidya-Dhana, whose history dates back to the Dharmasutras, presupposes the existence of the profession much earlier.

However, in this regard (Manu, VIII. 169), says that professional Lawyers were already in presence in the time of the Manava Code.

2. There is no such evidence from which we can infer that legal profession was also in existence in the modern sense of the expression at the time of the Smritis. However, the persons who were well versed in law were permitted to give some suggestions to the King and his councillors for their ponderings. This system of "expression of legal opinion" was similar to the *Responsa Prudentium* of the ancient Romans. The only duty of law expert persons was to give their opinions to the King. While these legal opinions were not binding upon the King; it was the sole discretion of the King whether to follow them or not.
3. Another writer P. Varadachariar's argued that: "It is not possible to say anything as to the presence of a legal profession in Ancient India." It gives the impression that he also recognizes the existence.
4. In this regard, the viewpoint of the Indian Dean of Dharmasastra is completely different. Interestingly, P. V. Kane, concerning the legal profession in ancient times, states:

An interesting question arises as to whether Lawyers as an institution were there in ancient India. The reply must be that, as far as the Smritis are concerned, there is nothing to indicate that there existed a category of individuals whose profession was the identical as that of a modern counsel, solicitors or legal practitioners and who were controlled by the State existed. He denies the existence of the legal practitioners.

3.3. The Textual data:

3.3.1. Narada

By analyzing the text of Narada a first point to be noted is that representation in a law court is not denoted to before the Naradasmṛti. Either representation did exist from an earlier time, but Narada was the first one to indicate the institution explicitly, or representation did not exist before Narada. In Jolly's translation of Naradasmṛti this means:

If a person is selected by the respondent or claimant as his representative and such person speaks in court for his client, the victory or defeat will affect the party himself and not the representative.

The second stanza of Narada as translated by Jolly speaks:

He deserves a punishment who speaks for someone else without being the brother, father, son or designated representative and who contradicts himself in the process.

From the second stanza the conclusion can be drawn, such as, as per Narada, a party could give to another person a *Niyoga* to speak and represent for him in the court. *Niyoga* means appointment.

3.3.2. Brhaspati

Concerning representation through Lawyers, the *Brhaspatismṛti* in its turn contains at least one sloka connected with representation. Jolly translates that:

For a lunatic, idiot, silly or crazy or elderly person and for women, minors and sick persons, a parent or designated representative should offer the trial or answer as their representative.

It is clear from this stanza that representation through Lawyers does exist and recognized according to wording of *Brhaspati*.

3.3.3. Katyayana

It is one of the most important book in which the representation through Lawyers is focused and argued. There is detailed chapter in connection with representation. It is famous out of all Dharmasastras. P. V. Kane collected no less than seven slokas on the subject; in his translation he organised them under the title "Substitutes or recognised agents of parties".

The first two slokas of (*Katyayana* 89-90) as translated by Kane are as follows:

A person other than the accused, if raised by the accused before the judge as an accused, must be considered an accused, as well as that who has been accepted by the plaintiff himself as an accused.

It is the right of the accused [to give a reply] and not to another person as he is not related [to the dispute]; [but] even a stranger can be granted [the right to defend himself] if he is put forward as the defendant] by the person charged [by the plaintiff].

It is clear that right to defend was allowed and recognized. Defendant may defend in his suit through Lawyer. In this connection the representation through Lawyers is very clear. Plaintiff has to appear through Lawyer i.e person acting as his representative. The Slokas of *Katyayana* are very clear and supports the existence of legal profession and pleading through representative.

3.3.4. Pitamaha

It is also necessary here to mention the text and verses of *Pitamaha*. These are translated by Scriba as follows:

The king should conduct a lawsuit when the father, the mother, a friend, a relative, or a servant appear [as representatives].

Whenever somebody engages another person to act in his behalf, it is as if the act was done by himself, and it cannot be negated.

The first Sloka is clear. It can be concluded that King should allow a party to be represented by his father, mother, friend, or relative. This stanza is very clear for existence of representative. The second stanza, following after the first, again allows various interpretations. Either it means that any one of those referred to before, when acting through niyoga, (appointment), acts in the other person's name. Or it indicates that anybody speaking for anybody else through niyoga is his real representative. In that case, niyoga does not refer to an "appointment" given to a specific class of representatives, but it suggests that anybody can be anybody's niyukta.

3.3.5. Sukranitisara

Sukranitisara also recognized representation of Lawyers. For Example, B. K. Sarkar's translation of Sukranitisara verse 108 reads as follows:

Representative has to be appointed by the plaintiff and defendant who know the legal procedure.

The elements found in Sukranitisara are summarized as:

1. Representatives are appointed by parties who are vyavaharanabhijna i.e who know the rules of legal procedure.
2. The payment of the niyojita or niyogin is dealt with in great detail.
3. The Niyogin must be chosen by the party, not by the king.

It hardly needs to be recalled that these elements played an important part in some of the opinions of modern scholars, as stated above. Here we may infer that representation was done through Lawyers because he is expert in legal procedures and know the legal theories and concepts in detail. He is supposed to be learned in laws of the land in which he is practicing. Plaintiffs also give payment to the Advocates. Parties appoint their representative and not King.

However, no written source allows us to draw the conclusion that the experts on legal matters ever developed into a professional group whose regular activities consisted in representing parties in the Court. The impression which we gather from the texts is that, even in cases where the representative was chosen because of his special competence on legal matters, and, a fortiori, in all other cases, the necessary condition for a person to represent a party was the existence, between the former and the latter, of a certain form of close personal relationship. In other words, he does not act as a professional expert (vyavaharaina) but as a personal friend (suhrd). The client discussed issue in great detail with their representatives. Professional expert was working for safeguarding rights of the litigants.

4. Conclusion:

It is concluded that during the reign of Aurangzeb, first time the Lawyers were appointed to plead before court of Law. Lawyers were used to appear before Court in suits against the state. They were appointed as full time Lawyers to defend state cases. Further, these Lawyers were also bound to give free advice to the poors . Such Lawyers were appointed in each District. Moreover, the office of the Vakil-e-Shara was fully equipped with helping staff comprises of an accountant along with three clerks. In particular he was attached to the Court of Qazi-e- Pargana. It can be deduced from the above that as a matter of fact, the entire Sukranitisara, is of recent origin.

It seems to be a more recent compilation based on a set of ancient rules - some of the verses are simply identical to those quoted in the Dharmasastras, but in which some very modern ideas have been inserted, even ideas from the Colonial Period. It is clear from the text of Sukranitisra that the professional experts were there and appointed by the parties as representative on their behalf.

Legally speaking, such professional experts are Lawyers because they were not appointed by the King but by parties. The parties give their consent to appoint Lawyers in order to decide their cases according to the Law. The lay man do not have deep knowledge of Law but Lawyers does have. The remuneration of the Lawyers was also given by parties.

It is all the more remarkable, as Varadachariar says, "that it provides for the appointment of a" representative "not only because of the party's ignorance in Vyavahara, but also because of his other occupation". This class of professional Lawyers shows that they were part of the old judicial system. However, Dharmasastra does not exclude the idea that the legal representative and the person represented should be linked by a personal bond of kinship, friendship, etc. This shows that, according to Classical Hindu Law, the parties have their representatives, known as Lawyers.

Such Lawyers are still present in various Indian courts. Their job is to give legal opinion on the question of law. They are also there to safeguard the rights and to secure the interests of other people. "Agents of social change" can be one of the roles of Lawyers that can be used in today's world. Thinking about one's client representation is quite important as well appropriate for establishing and promoting something for the help of others', although it is recommended that the public interest must also be kept in mind while doing so. Lawyers play significant role in a society for its betterment. Usually the talents of the Lawyers and their training both collectively often demonstrate a virtuous leadership in a social change activities.

Chronological Survey of Sanskrit Texts

- 1) Dharmasutras 600-300 B. C.
- 2) Dharmasutras
- 3) Manu 200 B. C.-100 A. D.
- 4) Yajnavalkya 100-300 A. D.
- 5) Narada 100-400 A. D.
- 6) Brhaspati 300-500 A. D.
- 7) Katyayana 400-600 A. D.
- 8) Vyasa 600-900 A. D.
- 9) Pitamaha 600-900 A. D.

Commentaries and Nibandhas

- 1) Asahaya on Narada 700-750 A. D.
- 2) Vyavaharacintamani 1500-1550 A. D.
- 3) Viramirodaya on Yajnavalkya 1615-1645 A. D.
- 4) Vivadarnavasetu 1773 A. D.

Art Haastra

- 1) Kautilya 300 B. C.-100 A. D.
- 2) Sukranitisara [1800 A. D.]

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Author Information

Dr. Rashida zahoore

Assistant Professor of Law Bahauddin Zakariya University Sub-Campus Vehari, Punjab, Postdoctoral Fellow at International Research Institute Islamabad, Pakistan.

Muhammad Asif Safdar

Assistant Professor Law, University Gilini Law College, Bahauddin Zakariya University(Corresponding Auhtor)

Khurram Baig, PhD Law Scholar

University Gilini Law College , Bahauddin Zakariya University , Multan, Advocate High Court

Waqas Ahamad

Lecturer Times Institute Multan
